

Exploring the role of digital technological relatedness for regional diversification into complex green technologies

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We shift attention to the development of green technologies in European regions, aiming to unveil the role played by digital knowledge in facilitating green diversification. Conceptually drawing on the literature on evolutionary economic geography, we construct indicators capturing different types of digital technological relatedness at the level of European regions drawn from regionalised patent data. By estimating a spatially lagged logit model (SLX), we find that related pre-existing digital technologies matter more for green than for non-green diversification. Further, while the existence of related digital technologies encourages regional development into complex green domains, our results suggest that regions do not rely on digital knowledge when diversifying into non-complex green technologies.

1. Introduction

Europe's transition towards a climate-neutral economy and society is deeply intertwined with the development of new green technologies (IEA, 2021; Montresor & Vezzani, 2023). In this context, the current European twin transition policy discourse has increasingly brought attention to potential synergies of green and digital technologies. It is argued that green and digital transitions are intrinsically linked, such that digitalization may accelerate the transition towards a greener economy (Montresor & Vezzani, 2023). There also exist evolutionary, conceptual arguments supporting the link between digital and green technologies. Digital technologies, as general-purpose technologies (GPTs), enable the codification of complex knowledge and facilitate the recombination of distant knowledge elements (Castellacci et al., 2020). At the same time, green technologies are typically interdisciplinary and therefore often a product of such recombinant innovation (Barbieri & Consoli, 2019), suggesting that digital technologies may indeed catalyse green technological development. What we also know from the literature is that recombinant innovation is particularly important for emerging, complex technologies¹ (Santoalha et al., 2021). It may thus further be argued that the nexus between digital and green technologies is particularly strong for more complex green technologies.

Despite initial studies exploring the influence of local digital skills and AI on green regional diversification, (Cicerone et al., 2023; Santoalha et al., 2021), the literature lacks a comprehensive empirical examination of how local specialisations in digital technologies might foster the emergence of green specialisations. Moreover, heterogeneities of green technologies concerning the complexity of their underlying knowledge domains are neglected so far (Barbieri et al., 2020). Against this background, we aim to advance this literature from a STI

¹ The notion of knowledge complexity has been dominant in recent geography of innovation literature. The ability to develop complex knowledge is regarded as an important factor in explaining technological development and economic advancement of regions and countries and if further considered as a major competitive advantage (Balland & Rigby, 2017). This competitive advantage that complex knowledge is associated with, arises from its inherently tacit nature, making it less accessible to external actors, and, consequently, spatially sticky, hard to imitate and more exclusive. Entering complex knowledge domains is therefore believed to require larger (economic) efforts (Broekel, 2019).

perspective by a broad, robust, and much more comprehensive empirical perspective mobilizing newest assets in innovation indicators development. We focus on green technology development in European regions, examining the role of digital technologies in facilitating green innovation. Our objectives are twofold: *First*, we estimate the impact of local – related and non-related – digital knowledge on the propensity of a region to develop a new specialisation in a (green) technology. Related digital knowledge is captured by relatedness density relying on the concept of related diversification², while the degree of digital specialisation is measured by the regional share of digital patents. *Second*, acknowledging the heterogeneous nature of green technologies in terms of their levels of complexity, we analyse whether related local digital specialisations are particularly important for developing new specialisations in more complex green technologies.

We approach the two objectives with a spatial version of the logit model (SLX), mobilising regional data on digital and green technologies over the period 1990-2019 (see Section 2). To account for the potential influence of spatial spillovers from neighbouring regions, we spatially lag all independent variables (see Section 3). Preliminary results are promising in context of recent literature and current policy debates, but also pave the way for some interesting future research ideas (see Section 4 and Section 5).

2. Data & Variables

To analyse the role played by digital knowledge for regional (green) technological diversification, we estimate the propensity of regions to specialise in a new (green) technology given existing local specialisations (from a conceptual perspective also referred to as entry model, see e.g., Boschma et al., 2015; Kogler et al., 2016; Rigby, 2015). We conduct the empirical analysis on 405 regions of the EU-27 countries, as well as Norway and the UK for the period of 1990-2019, aggregating the data in six non-overlapping five-year periods (1990-1994, ..., 2015-2019). The dependent and the main independent variables are calculated using patent data, obtained from the OECD's REGPAT database. The patent data are regionalised based on the location of the inventor, using the NUTS adapted regional classification³ (Villard et al., 2023).

For detecting green and digital patents, we work with technologies on the three-digit level, using the union of the Cooperative Patent Classification (CPC) and International Patent Classification (IPC). For green technologies, we mobilise the classification of environment-related technologies from the OECD ENV-TECH, where certain IPC and CPC technology-codes are classified as green, based on keywords (Hašičič & Migotto, 2015). We only consider a patent as green if it contains the full environment-related IPC/CPC code, rather than only its first three digits.⁴ Digital transformation has often been discussed with an emphasis on AI (see e.g. Cicerone et al., 2023), however, digital technologies consist of a broad spectrum to be taken into account for this study (Bianchini et al., 2023). For a more holistic perspective, we employ the definition of Information and Communication Technology Classification (ICT) of the OECD combined with the WIPO AI classification (OECD, 2015; WIPO, 2019). We use the

² The notion of related diversification is central to the evolutionary literature on technological path development. It refers to the well accepted idea that new technologies are typically embedded in existing local capabilities, meaning that regions tend to develop new specialisations in technology fields that are related to the existing local technological knowledge domains (see e.g., Boschma et al., 2015; Rigby, 2015).

³ The NUTS adapted classification includes Eurostat's metropolitan regions (aggregated NUTS 3 regions), and NUTS 2 regions for the remaining non-urban areas. A few NUTS3 regions with sizeable knowledge production, such as Oxford or Leuven, are singled out and enter on NUTS3 level.

⁴ In contrast to our approach, many researchers in the past have classified a patent as environment-related if it contains the first digits of an IPC/CPC code that is considered as environment related according to the ENVTECH classification (see e.g. Montresor and Quatraro, 2020). This, however, results in a substantial overestimation of green patents.

same approach as for green technologies, meaning that we identify a patent as digital if it contains the full code of an AI or IPC technology. We identify 26 three-digit environment-related classes and 21 three-digit digital classes for which there are (sufficient) data on patent applications in our OECD REGPAT dataset and a total of 167 three-digit IPC/CPC technology classes, including green and digital technology classes such as technologies that are neither green nor digital.

2.1 Indicators to track new technological specialisation (Dependent variable)

The dependent variable captures the emergence of a new technological specialisation – in the following also referred to as new entry. To identify such specialisations, we use the concept of the revealed technological advantage (RTA) (Soete, 1987), calculated for each region i ($i = 1, \dots, n$), technology k ($k = 1, \dots, K$) and period t ($t = 1, \dots, T$) by:

$$RTA_{ik,t} = \begin{cases} \frac{P_{ik,t} / \sum_k P_{ik,t}}{\sum_i P_{ik,t} / \sum_i \sum_k P_{ik,t}}, & \text{if } P_{ik,t} \geq 3 \\ 0, & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

$P_{ik,t}$ reflects the total number of patents in technology class k in region i and period t . Accordingly, region i has a specialisation in technology k if the share of technology k in the region's patent portfolio is higher than the share of technology k in the patent portfolio aggregated over the whole sample of n regions, i.e., $RTA > 1$. Further, to ensure that a region does not have a specialisation based on a very small total number of patents, we set a threshold, so that region i can only be specialised in technology k , if it has at least three patents in this technology.

The dependent variable is then constructed by the indicator *new entry* ($E_{ik,t}$) in a technology k ($k = 1, \dots, K$), is defined as follows:

$$E_{ik,t} = 1 \text{ if } RTA_{ik,t-1} \leq 1 \wedge RTA_{ik,t} > 1 \wedge P_{ik,t} - P_{ik,t-1} \geq 3 \wedge RTA_{ik,t} - RTA_{ik,t-1} > 0.3, \quad (2)$$

where $E_{ik,t}$ is binary taking the value of 1 for region i , period t and technology k , if (i) the region did not have a specialisation in technology k in the period $t - 1$ and acquires that specialisation in period t ; (ii) the absolute number of patents in technology k has increased by at least three from period $t - 1$ to period t ; and (iii) the $RTA_{ik,t}$ has increased by at least 0.3. The last two conditions are imposed to ensure that we do not identify a new green entry based on a very small increase of the RTA or even based on a decrease of total patents.

To address our second objective, namely whether the existence of a local digital knowledge base is even more important for the development of new *complex* green technologies, we separate our sample into complex and non-complex green technologies, meaning that we need to assess the complexity level of our 26 green technologies. We do so by employing the complexity measure as defined by Pintar and Scherngell (2022).⁵ It is based on the economic

⁵ As this complexity approach is sensitive to the granularity of the technology classification (Pintar and Essletzbichler, 2022), we calculate two alternative complexity measures to control for robustness of our obtained complex technologies. *First*, we aggregate the IPC3 technologies in the 35 Schmoch technologies and calculate a complexity value for each Schmoch technology, again based on the approach of Pintar and Scherngell (2022). We then assign the complexity level of the respective Schmoch technology class to each IPC3 technology class. *Second*, we also assess the complexity values of green and non-green IPC3 classes using the economic fitness index (EFC) (for details see Tacchella et al., 2012; Barbieri et al., 2023). As the results of the econometric analysis are robust, we proceed with the original approach.

complexity measure of Hidalgo and Hausmann (2009), which was originally invented to analyse the complexity of exported products. Applied in the context of knowledge complexity, the method reflects how sophisticated capabilities required for innovation in a certain technology are (Balland & Rigby, 2017; Barbieri & Consoli, 2019). In an iterative approach, information about the technologies in which regions are active in is used to simultaneously assess the complexity of each technology class and each region. The underlying idea is that technologies with a low ubiquity, i.e., technologies that not a lot of regions are able to produce knowledge in, and that are at the same time present in regions that are active in a large variety of technologies, are more complex (Pintar & Scherngell, 2022). We then divide our green technologies in a set of high- and low-complex green technologies, where a technology is defined to be complex if its calculated complexity level is above the median complexity of all green technologies.

2.2. Indicators to trace regional digital knowledge (explanatory variables)

Turning to the main explanatory variables, we focus on indicators to trace regional digital knowledge as a driver of for green diversification. We distinguish:

- i) Relatedness density
- ii) (Non-)digital relatedness density
- iii) Digital share

that are described in some more detail in what follows.

Relatedness density traditionally accounts for the idea that existing technological specialisations encourage diversification into related technologies (Hidalgo et al., 2018). It is calculated at the technology-region level and captures for each (green) technology k , how related it is to the existing knowledge portfolio of a region i . To construct the variable, we first calculate a measure for technological proximity. Making use of the fact that patent documents typically list more than one technology class, technological proximity, ϕ_{kl} , ($k, l = 1, \dots, K$), is obtained as the standardised co-occurrence, of any two technology fields k and l on the same patent document.⁶ Second, we combine the RTA index described above with the measure of technological proximity and obtain relatedness density as follows (note that time index t is omitted for eased readability):

$$\text{Relatedness density}_{ik} = \frac{\sum_{l \neq k} M_{il} \phi_{kl}}{\sum_{l \neq k} \phi_{kl}}, \quad (4)$$

where $M_{il} = 1$ if $RTA \geq 1$ and 0 otherwise. Relatedness, R_{ik} , is constructed as the sum of technological proximity, ϕ , of technology k to all technologies region i is specialised in, divided by the sum of technological relatedness of class k to all technology classes l . By construction, the value ranges between 0 and 1. A value of 0 indicates that region i is not specialised in any technologies related to technology k , while the value is equal to 1 if the region is specialised in all technologies related to a green technology k .

To assess how the role of digital technologies differs for regional green diversification, as compared to diversification into non-green technologies, we need to decompose the general relatedness density by constructing two variables reflecting the regional digital knowledge space; *digital relatedness density* and *non-digital relatedness density*. Here, we break down the

⁶ We calculate a technological proximity matrix for each period to consider potential changes in the proximity structure of the technologies. The standardisation of the co-occurrence value is done using the approach of Steijn (2020).

relatedness density indicator as explained above in two components, reflecting relatedness of the digital and non-digital knowledge base to a certain (green) technology k :

$$\text{Digital Relatedness density}_{ik} = \frac{\sum_{l,l \neq k} M_{il} \phi_{kl} \times \text{Digital}_l}{\sum_{l,l \neq k} \phi_{kl}}, \quad (5)$$

$$\text{Non - digital Relatedness density}_{ik} = \frac{\sum_{l,l \neq k} M_{il} \phi_{kl} \times \text{Non-Digital}_l}{\sum_{l,l \neq k} \phi_{kl}}, \quad (6)$$

where $\text{digital}_l = 1$ if technology l is classified as digital and 0 otherwise; and $\text{non-digital}_l = 1$ if technology l is not a digital technology and 0 otherwise.

Moreover, to assess whether local digital knowledge is generally more important for green as compared to non-green diversification, – independent from whether the existing digital domains are related to the newly entered technologies – we additionally construct a variable reflecting *digital share*. It is calculated as the number of regional patents that list at least one digital technology class, divided by the total number of regional patents.

We also add some control variables at the regional level. We include the non-fractionally counted logged number of annual patent applications, obtained from the OECD's REGPAT database to control for the total amount of patenting activity performed in the region. Further, we include the logged level of GDP per capita (obtained from the Ardeco database) to control for different levels of economic development.

3. Model & Econometric strategy

To model the relationship between green diversification – as captured by the entry in to a new (green) technology – and digital knowledge, we employ a spatially lagged X (SLX) logit model⁷. We choose the SLX approach – including all explanatory variables in their spatially lagged form – to account for the fact that in our multi-regional setting regions are not independent units but may in fact be influenced by the innovation activities of neighbouring regions, for example via spatially bounded knowledge spillovers (Jaffe et al., 1993). The analysis is done on the technology-region level, so that every unit of observation reflects region i , ($i = 1, \dots, n$), and technology k , ($k = 1, \dots, K$). A general model is specified as follows:

$$E_{ik,t} = \beta X_{ik,t-1} + \gamma Z_{i,t-1} + \theta W X_{ik,t-1} + \delta W Z_{ik,t-1} + \alpha_i + \eta_k + \tau_t + \varepsilon_{ik,t-1} \quad (7)$$

The binary dependent variable $E_{ik,t}$ reflects whether region i has entered a new specialisation in technology k , in period t . All explanatory variables are lagged by one period. This is a well-accepted approach to reduce endogeneity and the risk of reversed causality (Montresor & Vezzani, 2023; Moreno & Ocampo-Corrales, 2022). $X_{ik,t-1}$ reflects the main independent variables that include relatedness density and digital share or digital relatedness density and non-digital relatedness density. $Z_{i,t-1}$ denotes the vector of lagged control variables as specified above. W represents an $n - by - n$ row standardised spatial weights matrix, which describes the connectivity of the regions and is constructed based on an 8-nearest-neighbours definition of neighbourhood. We introduce a region-fixed effect, α_i , a period-fixed effect, τ_t , and a technology fixed effect, η_g .

⁷ Deviating from previous empirical studies which often chose a linear probability model (LPM) (see e.g., Santoalha et al., 2020), we deem that a logit model is better suited for our research framework. The logit model deals with the binary nature of the dependent variable and allows for the prediction of bounded probabilities. We however also estimate an LPM model to confirm robustness of our results.

The econometric strategy is the following. For our first research objective concerning the importance of (related) digital technologies for green vs. non-green diversification, we divide our sample in green versus non-green technologies. To address the second aim of the study, we moreover run the analysis separately for the sample of complex versus non-complex green technologies.

4. Results

As an exploratory prelude to the modelling exercise, the maps in Figure 1 illustrate the number of specialisations regions have in green and digital technologies (based on results from equation 1). While for digital technologies the large metropolitan centres, such as London, Paris, Berlin, Dublin and Munich, exhibit the highest number of specialisations, regions with diverse green knowledge are located in Northern Italy and Southern France, Denmark and Finland. While there seem to be big disparities in the number of digital specialisations between urban and rural areas, the distribution of green specialisations appears to be somewhat more even. Note, however, that a various Eastern European and some Southern European regions drop out of our analysis as they do not produce enough patents to calculate meaningful variables.

Figure 1: Number of digital (left) and green (right) specialisations in the period 2010-2014. Note: Coloured using natural breaks.

The first part of our econometric analysis shifts attention to the share of digital patents in the regional knowledge base (see Table 1). To evaluate whether a high digital share of patents is more important for green diversification than for diversification in non-green technologies, we separately estimate the logit model for the 26 green technologies (models 1 and 2) and the remaining 120 non-green and non-digital technologies (models 3 and 4).

Table 1: Effects of digital knowledge on green versus non-green diversification

	GREEN ENTRY		NON-GREEN ENTRY	
	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)
<i>Relatedness density</i>	0.024*** (0.005)	-	0.025*** (0.002)	-
<i>Digital share</i>	1.624** (0.699)	-	0.763** (0.337)	-
<i>Digital relatedness density</i>	-	0.065*** (0.006)	-	0.041*** (0.006)
<i>Non-digital relatedness density</i>	-	0.019*** (0.004)	-	0.024*** (0.002)
<i>W Relatedness density</i>	0.019*** (0.0070)	-	0.035*** (0.003)	-
<i>W Digital share</i>	0.951 (1.294)	-	1.035* (0.560)	-
<i>W Digital relatedness density</i>	-	-0.001 (0.011)	-	0.016 (0.010)
<i>W Non-digital relatedness density</i>	-	0.021*** (0.007)	-	0,037*** (0.003)
<i>Patents (log)</i>	-0.176 (0.147)	-0.119 (0.140)	-0.005 (0.074)	0.010 (0.072)
<i>GDP per cap. (log)</i>	0.494 (0.736)	0.547 (0.729)	0.741** (0.298)	0.805*** (0.308)
<i>W Patents (log)</i>	0.124 (0.265)	2.246* (1.27)	-0.053 (0.110)	0.347 (0.438)
<i>W GDP per cap. (log)</i>	1,954 (1.305)	0.115 (0.265)	0.163 (0.429)	-0.030 (0.110)
<i>Observations</i>	38.598	38.546	173.766	173.295
<i>Pseudo R²</i>	0.20	0.20	0.11	0.11
<i>BIC</i>	15,673	15,654	72,233	72,234

Note: Significance codes: ***: 0.01, **: 0.05, *: 0.1, Clustered (Region FE & IPC) standard-errors in parentheses; all models are estimated with region, time and period fixed effects.

Comparing the identified effects, we find similar magnitudes for the green and non-green technologies. Relatedness density is significant for both green and non-green diversification. This is in line with previous works (Moreno & Ocampo-Corrales, 2022; Santoalha & Boschma, 2021). It highlights that regions typically develop new specialisations in domains that are not too distant from the local knowledge base and that technological diversification plausibly occurs by building on existing know-how (Boschma et al., 2015). The regional propensity to develop a new specialisation further positively correlates with the share of digital patents in the local knowledge portfolio for both green and non-green technologies. Even though a higher share of digital knowledge is positively associated with both the development of green and non-

green technologies, this relationship is statistically stronger for green technologies.⁸ We further find that the impact of relatedness density is larger for non-green than for green entries, which is in line with recent studies of Montresor and Quatraro (2020) or Santoalha et al. (2021). The finding resonates with the argument that that green innovations tend to be more radical, drawing from an ample pool of know-how and combining previously unrelated domains.

Turning to a key point of interests, namely the effect of digital and non-digital relatedness density, we find – as expected – a positive significant effect of both variables for both the green and non-green entry model. This implies that for both branching into a new green and a new non-green technology, regional actors exploit complementarities with respect to their existing digital and non-digital knowledge base. However, interestingly the effect of digital relatedness is much higher than that of non-digital relatedness, i.e., regions rely stronger on pre-existing related digital than on related non-digital technologies.

Concerning the role of spatial spillovers from neighbouring regions, as captured by our spatially lagged control variables, we find that a region is more likely to develop a specialisation in a certain technology, if its neighbouring region has capabilities that are related to this technology. This is reflected by the positive significant effect of the spatially lagged relatedness density (*W Relatedness density*) and the spatially lagged non-digital relatedness density (*W Non-digital relatedness density*). Interestingly, we do not observe a positive impact for the spatially lagged digital relatedness density. Indicating that while regional actors seem to benefit from related knowledge in neighbouring regions in non-digital technologies for their branching process, they are unable to tap digital knowledge from neighbouring regions. This may reflect a reduced accessibility of digital knowledge.

Table 2: Effects of digital knowledge for the diversification into complex versus non-complex green technologies

	GREEN ENTRY			
	complex technologies		non-complex technologies	
<i>Relatedness density</i>	0.021** (0.008)	-	0.024*** (0.004)	-
<i>Digital share</i>	1.819* (0.952)	-	0.922 (0.884)	-
<i>Digital relatedness density</i>	-	0.076*** (0.007)	-	-0.073 (0.098)
<i>Non-digital relatedness density</i>	-	0.009* (0.003)	-	0.025*** (0.004)
<i>W Relatedness density</i>	0.007 (0.009)	-	0.027** (0.009)	-
<i>W Digital share</i>	2.995* (1.754)	-	1.313 (1.651)	-

⁸ We confirmed that there is a significant difference between the effect by running a model with green and non-green entries, interacting the digital share variable with a dummy variable indicating green technologies.

<i>W Digital relatedness density</i>	-	-0.0083 (0.018)	-	0.0633 (0.100)
<i>W Non-digital relatedness density</i>	-	0.010 (0.011)	-	0.028*** (0.009)
<i>Patents (log)</i>	-0.308 (0.212)	-0.222 (0.197)	0.038 (0.206)	0.069 (0.205)
<i>GDP p. cap. (log)</i>	0.940 (0.957)	0.945 (0.967)	0.076 (1.172)	0.173 (1.137)
<i>W Patents (log)</i>	0.507 (0.319)	0.576* (0.343)	-0.3801 (0.4650)	-0.410 (0.468)
<i>W GDP p. cap. (log)</i>	0.055 (1.162)	0.859 (1.545)	3.985* (2.190)	3.817* (2.096)
<i>Observations</i>	17.287	17.287	16.046	16.046
<i>Pseudo R2</i>	0.22	0.23	0.20	0.20
<i>BIC</i>	9,489	9,456	8,126	8,125

Note: Significance codes: ***: 0.01, **: 0.05, *: 0.1, Clustered (Region FE & IPC) standard-errors in parentheses; all models are estimated with region-, time- and period-fixed effects.

Addressing the second aim of the study, we run the model separately for high-complex and low-complex green technologies.⁹ The results, as presented in Table 2, reveal a positive association between digital share and entry into complex green technologies, whereas no such positive effect is observed for non-complex green technologies. Similarly, we also find that local specialisations in related digital technologies do not have an effect for the development of low complex green technologies, while the effect for complex green technologies is again positive and significant.¹⁰ This supports the theoretical argumentation that digital knowledge, e.g., in form of information and communication technologies, facilitates the codification of complex knowledge and thereby the emergence of recombinant innovation. These findings indicate that digital knowledge is not universally intertwined with all green knowledge domains, but rather holds significance for specific green knowledge fields – particularly those that are relatively scarce, not universally generated, and more challenging to replicate.

Concerning the control variables, we find that GDP per capita is positive and significant for most model specifications. The other control variable, number of patents is mostly insignificant, suggesting that its effect is captured by the region fixed effects. When running the models without fixed effects (see Appendix Table A 2), we find that the logged number of patents is, as expected, positively associated with a new entry in a technology.

⁹ We closely follow Pintar and Scherngell (2022) to assess the levels of complexity of the green technology classes.

¹⁰ To guarantee that the positive effect of digital relatedness density is not only driven by the IPC class of Y02D (Climate change mitigation technologies in information and communication technologies), which is identified as a complex technology, we run a robustness check where we exclude the technology class from the sample of complex technologies and find that the effect remains the same.

6. Conclusion

Twin green and digital transition are high on the policy agenda of the European Union. There is great hope that digitalization and the transition towards a green economy may pave the way for inclusive and sustainable regional development – both in economic and environmental terms. Despite a growing number of studies that analyse digital and green transition in isolation (Barbieri & Consoli, 2019; Moreno & Ocampo-Corrales, 2022; Santoalha & Boschma, 2021), the extent to which digital specialisations can reinforce green technological development at the regional level has so far not been thoroughly investigated by the existing empirical literature. In an attempt to fill this gap, we have investigated whether empirical paths of regional green diversification are indeed being reinforced by pre-existing digital technologies. The empirical analysis is carried out by means of a spatial version of the logit model for a panel of 405 European regions, spanning the period 1990-2019. Our main aim was to identify differences in the role played by local digital knowledge in the process of green vs. non-green diversification.

Our results suggest that digital knowledge – operationalised by the share of patents in ICTs and AI and digital relatedness density – is an important enabler of diversification for all technologies. It is however more important for green than for non-green diversification. This observation is consistent with the logic of twin transition and underlines the assumption that digital transition is thought to hold potential to drive sustainability goals and encourage green innovation. We also found that the impact of digital knowledge on the entry into green technologies varies based on the complexity of the green technologies. While both digital relatedness density and the share of digital patents has a positive effect on the development of complex green technologies, regions do not rely on related digital technologies when diversifying into non-complex green technologies. This finding suggests that digital knowledge is not a natural twin of all green knowledge domains, but only important for certain green knowledge fields, namely those which are scarcer, not universally produced, and harder to imitate.

6. References

- Balland, P.-A., & Rigby, D. (2017). The Geography of Complex Knowledge. *Economic Geography*, 93(1), 1–23. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00130095.2016.1205947>
- Barbieri, N., & Consoli, D. (2019). Regional diversification and green employment in US metropolitan areas. *Research Policy*, 48(3), 693–705. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.respol.2018.11.001>
- Barbieri, N., Consoli, D., Napolitano, L., Perruchas, F., Pugliese, E., & Sbardella, A. (2023). Regional technological capabilities and green opportunities in Europe. *The Journal of Technology Transfer*, 48(2), 749–778. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10961-022-09952-y>
- Barbieri, N., Marzucchi, A., & Rizzo, U. (2020). Knowledge sources and impacts on subsequent inventions: Do green technologies differ from non-green ones? *Research Policy*, 49(2), 103901. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.respol.2019.103901>

Bianchini, S., Damioli, G., & Ghisetti, C. (2023). The environmental effects of the "twin" green and digital transition in European regions. *Environmental & Resource Economics*, 84(4), 877–918. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10640-022-00741-7>

Boschma, R., Balland, P.-A., & Kogler, D. F [D. F.] (2015). Relatedness and technological change in cities: the rise and fall of technological knowledge in US metropolitan areas from 1981 to 2010. *Industrial and Corporate Change*, 24(1), 223–250. <https://doi.org/10.1093/icc/dtu012>

Cicerone, G., Faggian, A., Montresor, S., & Rentocchini, F. (2023). Regional artificial intelligence and the geography of environmental technologies: does local AI knowledge help regional green-tech specialisation ? *Regional Studies*, 57(2), 330–343. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00343404.2022.2092610>

De Marchi, V. (2012). Environmental innovation and R&D cooperation: Empirical evidence from Spanish manufacturing firms. *Research Policy*, 41(3), 614–623. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.respol.2011.10.002>

European Commission. (2020). *A New Industrial Strategy for a Green and Digital Europe*. https://commission.europa.eu/strategy-and-policy/priorities-2019-2024/europe-fit-digital-age/european-industrial-strategy_en#accelerating-twin-transitions

Haščič, I., & Migotto, M. (2015). *Measuring environmental innovation using patent data* (No. 89). OECD Publishing. <https://ideas.repec.org/p/oec/envaaa/89-en.html>
<https://doi.org/10.1787/5js009kf48xw-en>

Hidalgo, C. A., Balland, P.-A., Boschma, R., Delgado, M., Feldman, M., Frenken, K., Glaeser, E., He, C., Kogler, D. F., Morrison, A., Neffke, F., Rigby, D., Stern, S., Zheng, S., & Zhu, S. (2018). Correction to: The Principle of Relatedness. In A. J. Morales, C. Gershenson, D. Braha, A. A. Minai, & Y. Bar-Yam (Eds.), *Springer Proceedings in Complexity. Unifying Themes in Complex Systems IX (C1-C1)*. Springer International Publishing. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-96661-8_52

Hidalgo, C. A., & Hausmann, R. (2009). The building blocks of economic complexity. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences of the United States of America*, 106(26), 10570–10575. <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.0900943106>

Horbach, J., Oltra, V., & Belin, J. (2013). Determinants and Specificities of Eco-Innovations Compared to Other Innovations—An Econometric Analysis for the French and German Industry Based on the Community Innovation Survey. *Industry and Innovation*, 20(6), 523–543. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13662716.2013.833375>

IEA. (2021). *World Energy Outlook 2021*. IEA. <https://www.iea.org/reports/world-energy-outlook-2021>

- Jaffe, A. B., Trajtenberg, M., & Henderson, R. (1993). Geographic Localization of Knowledge Spillovers as Evidenced by Patent Citations. *The Quarterly Journal of Economics*, *108*(3), 577–598. <https://doi.org/10.2307/2118401>
- Li, D., Heimeriks, G., & Alkemade, F. (2021). Recombinant invention in solar photovoltaic technology: can geographical proximity bridge technological distance? *Regional Studies*, *55*(4), 605–616. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00343404.2020.1839639>
- Montresor, S., & Quatraro, F. (2020). Green technologies and Smart Specialisation strategies: a European patent-based analysis of the intertwining of technological relatedness and key enabling technologies. *Regional Studies*, *54*(10), 1354–1365. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00343404.2019.1648784>
- Montresor, S., & Vezzani, A. (2023). Digital technologies and eco-innovation. Evidence of the twin transition from Italian firms. *Industry and Innovation*, *30*(7), 766–800. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13662716.2023.2213179>
- Moreno, R., & Ocampo-Corrales, D. (2022). The ability of European regions to diversify in renewable energies: The role of technological relatedness. *Research Policy*, *51*(5), 104508. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.respol.2022.104508>
- OECD: Environment Working Papers*. (2015). <https://doi.org/10.1787/5js009kf48xw-en>
- Pintar, N., & Essletzbichler, J. (2022). *Complexity and smart specialisation : Comparing and evaluating knowledge complexity measures for European city-regions: Complexity and smart specialisation : Comparing and evaluating knowledge complexity measures for European city-regions*. https://www-sre.wu.ac.at/sre-disc/geo-disc-2022_04.pdf
- Pintar, N., & Scherngell, T. (2022). The complex nature of regional knowledge production: Evidence on European regions. *Research Policy*, *51*(8), 104170. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.respol.2020.104170>
- Rigby, D. L. (2015). Technological Relatedness and Knowledge Space: Entry and Exit of US Cities from Patent Classes. *Regional Studies*, *49*(11), 1922–1937. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00343404.2013.854878>
- Santoalha, A., & Boschma, R. (2021). Diversifying in green technologies in European regions: does political support matter? *Regional Studies*, *55*(2), 182–195. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00343404.2020.1744122>
- Santoalha, A., Consoli, D., & Castellacci, F. (2021). Digital skills, relatedness and green diversification: A study of European regions. *Research Policy*, *50*(9), 104340. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.respol.2021.104340>
- Soete, L. (1987). The impact of technological innovation on international trade patterns: The evidence reconsidered. *Research Policy*, *16*(2-4), 101–130. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0048-7333\(87\)90026-6](https://doi.org/10.1016/0048-7333(87)90026-6)

Tacchella, A., Cristelli, M., Caldarelli, G., Gabrielli, A., & Pietronero, L. (2012). A new metrics for countries' fitness and products' complexity. *Scientific Reports*, 2, 723. <https://doi.org/10.1038/srep00723>

WIPO. (2019). Artificial Intelligence: Technology Trends.

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All calculations were done in R. The source code is available upon request. All data are openly available. The calculation of the technology indicators is based on data drawn from the OECD's REGPAT database. Data on the control variables was partly obtained from the Ardeco database.

Author contributions

Theresa Bürscher: Conceptualisation, Methodology, Formal analysis, Data curation, Writing, Visualisation. **Thomas Scherngell:** Conceptualisation, Methodology, Validation, Writing, Supervision. **Martina Neuländtner:** Conceptualisation, Methodology, Validation, Writing.

Competing interests

The authors declare that they have no competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.